

Transcription Management System

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ABSTRACT

Transcription Management System automates an entire workflow of voice and transcripts files with a very simple and easier manner. The complete synthesis is based on interactive voice response where user can record their information in terms of audio file. Recent Admission Management Systems are often being breached for the visually impaired persons. They need to depend on another person for filling any kinds of forms. So our project helps such kind of people to fill their forms by recording voice. Any kind of user can utilize this system and reduce their time by storing data in wave format instead of typing via keyboard.

Filling Admission forms can be done by Transcription Management System with a smart indication. This composition can be used in any application, where person's vision is the critical issue. The features of this system are automatic transmission of voice files with just a couple of click. By just simple mouse clicks and speech inputs the system is easy to get along with any type of users; there is no need to remember keyboard. This system works on role basis like Translator, Manager and Reviewer. The visually impaired persons need not worry as they can listen to the prompting done by the system and perform respective actions.

Keywords: *Transcription, Transcripts, Visually impaired*

1. INTRODUCTION:

People who are physically impaired are not able to fill forms. As in recent systems it's tedious and needs extra hard work for them to fill any kinds of forms

online. So it is very difficult for them to live in the era of internet.

Transcription Management System simply makes their work in smoother manner which includes one dashboard with login of three different people. The blind person's need not to worry as they can listen to the prompting done by the system and perform respective actions.

1.1 LITERATURE SURVEY

In old systems, the blind person's need to use some specific languages to interact with the computer system. It's must for them to learn the specific languages available for them. ALVA Braille [1] is the language for blind persons. The output of language is on Braille bar [2].

Another development is Haptic Technology [3] in which shapes on the screen is feel by the blind user using their hands. Optical Character Recognition (OCR) Technology [4] extracts text from images which enables blind people to obtain printed, typewritten text. To achieve that, assistance in positioning on the paper-based form is required.

2. ARCHITECTURE

The web-based system application contains, database and four different roles. In this system user can access the web application and whatever data interaction done, it handles at background. Mainly the system is developed in the concern of blind persons. So, there are majorly three roles as follows: 1) Translator 2) Reviewer 3) Manager

Diagram: Transcription Management System

- Reviewer
- User
- Create role
- Assign Task
- Translator Task

A. Login

The first page is the Login/Register Page followed by the Manager login page who has all rights regarding modification and deletion roles i.e. assigning role, creating role etc.

2.1 WORKING

- **Translator:** Translator translates the voice data into text format. Wave files can get translated into text format through translator. Then the file is getting submitted to reviewer.
- **Reviewer:** Reviewer is responsible for validate the data translated by translator. He checked whether the translated data is correct or not. He can work like moderator, who checks the data, if correction are required then validate it; or otherwise send it back to the translator.
- **Manager:** Manager have all the authorities to access the data. He can modify or reject the data. Manager manages all translators and reviewers and their payment system. As well as manager assigns task to different translator and manage the data. He can fetch the record from database and assign it to translator. And at the final stage when every recorded data is converted into text format then confirmation call is getting send to the specific user.

B. Manager : Task Assign

Manager page has home page in which he can assign task, creates roles, can view Translated task and see the review records done by the reviewer. In this screenshot Manager can assign the task to Transcripotor or reviewer.

3. The Transcription Management System Framework

The system framework is enables the blind users to actively participate in the admission process through web application. The typical screens presented to the viewer are

- Login/Register Page
- Manager
- Translator

C. Manager: Translated Task

ID	Date	Roll No	First Name	Middle Name	Last Name	Age	DOB	Qualification	Mobile	Gender	Email Id	Address	City	Pin Code	State	Remark	Create by	Date
59	12/31/2017 6:02:38 PM	101	k	k	k	1	2/1/2018 12:00:00 AM	h	889900899	Female	ij@gmail.com	k	k	4444	k	Information is complete	h	12/31/2017 6:02:38 PM
57	1/12/2018 5:00:17 PM	5	k	m	j	1	1/1/2018 12:00:00 AM	k	889900899	Female	ij@gmail.com	k	k	4444	k	Remark	j	1/12/2018 5:00:17 PM
58	1/12/2018 5:48:45 PM	10	narrata	arishah	ahire	20	1/2/1985 12:00:00 AM	BE	23326747	Female	narrata@gmail.com	aboyc	nasik	42303	mh	Remark	Savita	1/12/2018 5:48:45 PM
60	1/12/2018 6:07:04 PM	2	lalita	p	shird	20	1/9/1997 12:00:00 AM	BE	885363	Female	lalita@gmail.com	wepE3X	nasik	855	mh	Remark	Savita	1/12/2018 6:07:04 PM
63	3/4/2018 11:55:14 AM	1	xyz	www	hqqq	22	3/4/2018 12:00:00 AM	sd	41235542	Female	abc@gmail.com	76655haddh	nsk	14214	maharashtra	Remark		3/4/2018 11:55:14 AM

Translated task is only visible to manager. So he can does modification if needed any.

D. Translator Form

Translator is responsible to translate the inserted voice record into text format. He can listen the voice first one by one and then translate it into text form.

E. Reviewer:

Reviewer reviews the task translated by translator. He checked whether the translated data is correct or not. He can work like moderator, who checks the data, if correction are required then validate it; or otherwise send it back to the translator

F. User:

User is centralized part of the system. At front end user enters his information through the voice. And our system handles it at background.

4. FUTURE SCOPE

Transcription Management System is total interactive project. The software can be developed in all regional languages. As if now it is for admission system but

later it can be developed in all types of web based applications.

5. APPLICATION

The system is mainly designed to concern of blind persons. So, as to they can fill online as well as offline forms by their voice. It can be used in private institutions as well as in government sector. Normal persons can also use the system as it helps for them to save time.

6. CONCLUSION

The Transcription Management System is handled by visually impaired person as well as normal persons. It has feature of speech to text which makes those who have language problem as a barrier. Because of easier and faster access of data, there is a wide scope in future.

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REFERENCES

- 1) J. J. Lazzaro, "Helping the Web help the disabled," Spectrum, IEEE, vol.36,pp. 54-59,1999
- 2) H.Burton and D.G. McLaren, "Visual cortex activation in late-onset, Braille naïve blind individuals: an fMRI study during semantic and phonological task with heard words," Neuroscience letters, vol.392,pp. 38-42,2006.
- 3) C. Sjostrom developed "Haptic interface" in 2007.
- 4) Quantum Technology Products for people who are blind.
<http://www.quantumtechnology.com.au/blindness>, June 2015.

